

Appendix A Literature review

The Web of Science database was searched using the keyword “interactive data quality”. Only papers that explicitly addressed interactive Data Quality (DQ) tools and discussed user interface (UI) aspects were retained (chosen based on their titles and abstracts).

Table 1: IML for DQ studies.

Ref.	Short description	Techniques used	ML used?	UI	User eval.
[1]	DQ Advisor for interactive DQ assessment for any dataset. A user provides input data and receives a visual output in a dashboard.	Univariate checks, statistical analysis, ensemble anomaly detection	Yes	Jupyter Notebook	No
[2]	Interactive data cleaning system. Cleaning operators are applied to user-provided data, that is visualized after each transformation.	Statistical analysis, rule-based anomaly detection	No	Web app.	No
[3]	DQLearn: A toolkit for detecting and correcting DQ issues and applying DQ assessment rules, with visualizations and recommendations provided to a human.	Univariate checks, statistical analysis	No	Python API	No
[4]	Activeclean: a machine learning (ML) model training tool with data cleaning that takes a model and data as input a user and identifies points that, if cleaned, would change the predictions.	Custom cleaning operations provided by user	No	PySpark	No
[5]	MatrixQCvis: interactive visualization of DQ metrics and data preprocessing.	Detecting low quality samples, drift, outliers, etc.	No	Shiny app (R)	No
[6]	ADQuaTe2: interactive DQ learning incorporating expert feedback to retrain the model for improved accuracy.	Autoencoder for detection; Self Organizing Maps for clustering; Random Forest for explanations	Yes	Web interface	No
[7]	An interactive DQ tool that summarizes a dataset’s ability to fulfill its intended purpose, focusing on data completeness.	Feature distribution, percentages of missing/zero values	No	Shiny app (R)	Yes
[8]	Cleenex: data cleaning tool-graph supporting user involvement during an iterative data cleaning process.	Data transformations, user-defined DQ rules, manual data repairs	No	SQL /Java	Yes
	Our tool - IML4DQ: detecting DQ issues in an interactive way with explanations generated for detected issues	Ensemble of iForest [9] & Autoencoder [10]; Shapley Additive Explanations (SHAP) [11]	Yes	TKinter desktop app	Yes

Appendix B ML4DQ framework

ML4DQ framework [11] combines ML models (an ensemble of Isolation Forest [9] and Autoencoder [10] models) with explainable AI (Shapley Additive Explanations - SHAP [12,13]) to improve the quality of credit risk data. In particular, the ML part is used to detect DQ issues, while local SHAP explanations are generated in order to highlight problematic features that might cause the DQ issue. ML4DQ starts with extracting and preprocessing the data [11]. Then, an ensemble of ML models is used to detect anomalies (Fig. 1). Next, the observations are ranked according to the anomaly scores returned by the ensemble, and the top cases are returned for further investigation. SHAP explanations are generated for these cases to support this investigation. Top cases and their explanations are sent for further check by a DQ expert who decides whether the cases are truly problematic, resulting in either random DQ issues or systematically occurring cases that can be transformed into DQ artefacts.

Fig. 1: ML4DQ by [11]

Appendix C Feature engineering

Since the contract is stipulated at the loan level, the cover information is aggregated at the loan level when engineering the cover level features. Next, the data is preprocessed to obtain the features that represent data movements [11]. To obtain these movements, we calculate the difference between the logarithms of two adjacent months, $t - 1$ and t , as $x_{i,ratio} = \ln \frac{x_{i,t}}{x_{i,t-1}}$ [11]. We refer to these preprocessed movements as ratios. Depending on the granularity of the data, these ratios can be either daily (out of scope in ML4DQ) or monthly. The daily model type is not covered in the IML4DQ framework and is left for future research.

Table 2: Features

Feature	Description	Level
Risk-weighted assets (RWA)	The amount of risk that a bank incurs as a result of its activities, determined by weighting each asset based on its risk level.	Cover
Exposure at Default (EAD)	The amount of loss that a bank may experience as a result of failure. For loan commitments: Cover the amount of capacity that is expected to be drawn in the event of a default.	Cover
Loss Given Default (LGD)	A ratio of losses to an exposure at default. It is the opposite of Recovery Rate: $LGD = \text{Loan} - RR$.	Cover
Probability of Default (PD)	The likelihood that a borrower will fail to meet their contractual obligations and default.	Loan
Outstanding Amount	The portion of the exposure already drawn by the obligor.	Cover
Provisions	A portion of EAD that is visible in Profit/Loss.	Cover
Maximal Limit	Highest amount authorized for an applicant to borrow.	Loan
Risk Weight	Measure of relative riskiness (calculated as RWA/EAD)	Loan
Cover value	Loan protection insurance value	Cover

Appendix D UI design principles

Table 3: UI principles from [14] and their mapping to the IML4DQ design

Design principle	IML4DQ UI design
Offer informative feedback	Informing about the progress in the tool: progress bars, notifications of a task completion. Informing about the choices made in previous screens.
Strive for consistency	Consistent design of screens: consistent widgets/colors/layout.
Simple and natural dialog	A separate screen for each step with information relevant to that step; the final screen expands as the user progresses.
Prevent errors	Documentation explaining data preparation & application workings; informative titles of the widgets & screens; handling of negative paths and clear error messages.
Minimize user memory load	Overview of previous choices in the final screen; precalculated final outlier score & loans sorted based on it.

Appendix E Evaluation

E.1 Evaluation framework

The orange part of the evaluation examines the determinants of a general attitude towards detecting DQ problems. Our approach is inspired by [15] which employs Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) [16] to explore factors influencing data producers’ intentions to enter data correctly. TPB is based on Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA) [17], which posits that the intention to perform a particular behavior is influenced by attitude towards the behavior and subjective norms. Attitude encompasses the likely consequences of performing the behavior and is influenced by behavioral beliefs (affective aspects) and evaluations of behavioral outcomes (cognitive aspects) [17]. We refer to these as the “experiential” and “instrumental” determinants, respectively (Fig. 2). The subjective norm reflects social pressure (not) to perform the behavior, determined by normative beliefs and motivation to comply [17].

TPB adds a third determinant of intention: perceived behavioral control, representing an individual’s perceived capability in performing the behavior, i.e., self-efficacy [16]. However, since the job description of our interviewees includes working with data, they are inherently capable of performing DQ tasks. Hence, we use the original TRA model and omit the self-efficacy construct. For that same reason, we assume that the relationships between attitude, subjective norm, and intention established by the TRA hold, i.e., we take the model as given, with attitude and subjective norm positively influencing intention to detect DQ issues (hence, no questions for the intention construct in the TRA part of the evaluation). What we want to study are the antecedents of attitude and subjective norm, that is, the experiential and instrumental determinants of attitude and the determinants of subjective norm. For the latter, we distinguish three types of determinants according to the social group that exerts the pressure: management-based norms, government-based norms, and peer-based norms, since these three categories play a crucial role in credit risk. The literature also recommends distinguishing between social sources of influence [15].

Fig. 2: Evaluation design

The green part of the evaluation focuses on the IML4DQ framework itself, specifically the intention to interact with the ML system for detecting DQ issues. As we introduce new technology for the DQ task, we employ the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), another extension of the TRA, to investigate how users adopt and use technology [18]. The choice of TAM is also determined by its adoption in evaluation of interactive DQ solutions [7,8]. According to TAM, the factors influencing technology adoption include perceived usefulness (PU) and perceived ease of use (PEOU): the former assesses whether the technology effectively aids in the DQ issues detection task, and the latter determines if using the technology is “free from effort” [18]. In this context, PEOU is evaluated by the pleasantness of using the IML4DQ solution, which is assessed based on key UI design principles [14], comprising the third and final part of the evaluation (highlighted in red). The use of TAM in human-computer interaction is well aligned: [19] reports on their complementary perspectives, with TAM extending traditional UI methodologies.

We combine the TRA and TAM components into one model to account for the specific characteristics of the DQ domain: automating the DQ process only makes sense if there is a positive intention towards the process itself. Therefore, the determinants of the first part (TRA) are also crucial for the automation aspect (TAM). Each construct of the combined model is associated with a set of questions (Appendix E.3) to be asked during interviews. For most of the questions, the interviewee first provides an answer on a Likert scale, and is then invited to clarify the answers with open comments. Although a Likert scale is used, due to the limited number of interviews, no causal conclusions can be drawn. Instead, the evaluation aims to understand how each construct is established at the intersection of credit risk, DQ, and IML.

E.2 Interviewees profile

Table 4: Interviewees profile. All the experts are involved into the credit risk management projects.

Expert	Role	Field
Expert 1	Product Lead	Data Management
Expert 2	Product Lead Products	Data Management Retail
Expert 3	Financial Risk Specialist	Financial Risk
Expert 4	Analyst	Bus. Analytics and Modelling
Expert 5	Financial Risk Specialist	Financial Risk
Expert 6	Model developer	Bus. Analytics and Modelling
Expert 7	Strategic Change Expert	Financial Risk

E.3 Interview questions

For Q1-Q4, answer using the given Likert scale. For Q5-Q10, answer using the following Likert scale: *Strongly disagree - Disagree - Neutral - Agree - Strongly agree*. For Q11-Q18, answer in a free format. M - Management, G - Government, P - Peers. A - Attitude. E - Experiential. I - Instrumental.

1. **EA:** How difficult is it to manually identify DQ issues in general? Scale: *Very easy - Easy - Moderate - Difficult - Very difficult*
2. **IA:** How important do you think it is to automate the DQ process with statistics and ML? Scale: *Very insignificant - Insignificant - Moderate - Important - Very important*
3. **IA:** How useful is it to detect DQ issues for a financial institution? Scale: *Very useless - Useless - Moderate - Useful - Very useful*
4. **IA:** How big is the impact of DQ issues on credit risk estimation? Scale: *Very low - Low - Moderate - High - Very high*
5. **SN - M:** My management expects me to prevent DQ issues arising in the data.
6. **SN - M:** I feel it is important to comply with the management expectations about DQ.
7. **SN - G:** Governmental regulations expect me to prevent DQ issues.
8. **SN - G:** I feel it is important to comply with these regulations.
9. **SN - P:** My colleagues think dealing with DQ issues is not important.
10. **SN - P:** My work is not influenced by the attitude of my colleagues towards DQ.
11. **IML4DQ: A - PU:** Will the application help you identify DQ issues more quickly and easily?
12. **IML4DQ: A - PU:** Will the adoption of the DQ application increase the quality of credit risk data?
13. **IML4DQ: A - PEOU - Offer informative feedback:** Does the application offer informative feedback?
14. **IML4DQ: A - PEOU - Strive for consistency:** Do you feel like the tool is consistent in terms of widgets and use of color, format and layout of widgets?
15. **IML4DQ: A - PEOU - Prevent errors:** Are instructions clear enough to prevent you from making mistakes? Are error messages comprehensible enough to help you understand what went wrong?
16. **IML4DQ: A - PEOU - Minimize user's memory load:** Do you feel like you have to memorize what you did in the application as you move from one screen to the next?
17. **IML4DQ: A - PEOU - Simple and natural dialog:** Is it clear what the tool is asking you to do? In other words, do you understand what to do next? Do you find the tool's dialog easy to use and understand?
18. **IML4DQ - Intention:** If the application is deployed in production, would you use it?

Appendix F Results: output file layout

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L	M	N	O	P	Q	R	S	
1	Index	LOAN_ID	OS_R_x	OS_R_y	OS_RATIO	PROVISIONS_x	PROVISIONS_y	PROVISION_RATIO	EAD_R_x	EAD_R_y	EAD_RATIO	RWA_R_x	RWA_R_y	RWA_RATIO		Risk_weight_x	Risk_weight_y	Risk_weight_RATIO	Final_proba	
2	1				1.92			16.54			8.66			11.75	---				3.96	0.97
3	2				0.69			-6.41			0.00			-5.14	---				-5.14	0.90
4	3				-0.06			-5.20			-2.15			-5.70	---				-3.54	0.86
5	4				-0.69			6.45			-3.10			3.10	---				3.76	0.86
6	5				-0.06			-4.45			-2.15			-5.70	---				-3.54	0.86
7	6				0.72			-16.01			0.20			-3.35	---				-3.54	0.85
8	7				0.15			-15.42			-1.08			-4.63	---				-3.54	0.85
9	8				0.15			-15.42			-1.08			-4.63	---				-3.54	0.85
10	9				0.00			6.70			-0.20			3.49	---				3.69	0.85
11	10				-0.32			4.23			-0.18			3.50	---				3.69	0.85
12	11				-29.40			6.11			0.30			3.96	---				3.65	0.84
13	12				-29.03			5.93			0.06			3.72	---				3.65	0.83
14	13				0.25			-16.01			-0.77			-4.32	---				-3.55	0.83
15	14				-0.01			22.63			-0.01			-2.94	---				-2.94	0.83
16	15				0.09			-3.93			-1.50			-4.64	---				-3.55	0.83
17	16				-28.78			5.27			-0.01			3.67	---				3.67	0.83
18	17				0.02			23.08			0.02			-2.77	---				-2.79	0.82
19	18				0.02			22.56			0.02			-2.83	---				-2.84	0.82
20	19				0.02			22.73			0.02			-2.77	---				-2.79	0.82
21	20				0.00			23.27			0.00			-2.40	---				-2.40	0.82

(a) Results sheet

(b) SHAP for the Autoencoder sheet

(c) SHAP for iForest sheet

Fig. 3: Output file spreadsheets. The “Index” column helps locate the corresponding SHAP plots in the other sheets, where each plot is annotated with its index.

Appendix G Results: evaluation

Fig. 4: Attitude

Fig. 5: Subjective Norm

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